

x_d -index: An overall scholarly expertise index for the research portfolio management of institutions

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Abstract

Institutional performance assessment had always been and will remain as a key challenge to a multitude of stakeholders. Most of the existing indicators including h -type indicators and many others do not reflect the expertise of institutions that defines their research portfolio. Recently, a set of expertise measures such as x and $x(g)$ indices were introduced to reflect the expertise of institutions with respect to a specific discipline/field considering strengths in different finer level thematic areas. In this work, an adaptation of the x -index, namely the x_d -index is proposed to reflect the overall scholarly expertise of an institution considering its publication pattern and strength in different coarse thematic areas. This indicator is supposed to reflect the core expertise areas and also the diversity of the research portfolio of the institution. This indicator and associated framework are demonstrated on a dataset of 135 institutions. The ability to reflect diversity is validated by determining the correlation with a prominent diversity indicator. x_d -index is found to correlate with the major diversity indicator (Shannon's diversity index) with better values as compared to institutional h -index and g -index. Further, the possibilities for effective management of the research portfolio of an institution by expanding its diversity is discussed in this work, that may aid concerned stakeholders.

Keywords: Expertise index, Expertise diversity, Institutional performance assessment, Research portfolio, Research strength

Introduction

The institutional organization of science had played and might continue to play a very important role in the advancement of science, along with intellectual and social organizations of science. This growth is facilitated by various funding sources, including government and non-governmental agencies. Until a few decades ago, such funding was largely 'trust-based', which involved less use of efficient scientometric methods for the assessment of institutions for funding. But with the growth of the field of scientometrics and increased awareness about its potential, funding agencies started to adopt sharp performance assessment methods. The major motivation for the adoption of performance-based funding can be to ensure simultaneously (i) the 'vertical differentiation' and 'functional specialization' between the institutions and (ii) horizontal diversity and pluralism within the system (Sörlin, 2007). Some examples are (i) the formation of the Research Excellence Framework (REF) in the UK (De Boer et al., 2015) (ii) the allocation of AUD 80 million to universities based on performance-based funding by the Australian government (Maslen, 2019) and (iii) adoption of Norwegian model of funding at national level by Norway, Belgium (Flanders), Denmark, Finland and Portugal (Sivertsen, 2016). Due to this change in funding pattern, most institutions were forced to strive for a continuous improvement of performance.

The rise of several international and national ranking systems like QS, THE, ARWU, and

CWTS rankings is also witnessed in the last couple of decades. Most of the above-mentioned global ranking systems make use of different kinds of survey data, along with information such as (i) the number of publications in highly reputed/cream journals, (ii) number of the faculty and alumni with prestigious awards like Nobel Prizes and Fields Medals (Shanghai Ranking's Academic Ranking of World Universities, 2021), and/or (iii) other information such as grants. These methodologies are prone to bias and invited criticism. Billaut et al. (2010) has shown that ARWU used many irrelevant criteria, and the aggregation methodology has several limitations. Also, changing of relative weights placed upon each of the six factors of ARWU significantly alters the ranking (Jeremic et al., 2011). Similarly, the "arguably the most influential" THE rankings (Beck & Morrow, 2010), is susceptible to an anchoring effect on the ratings (Bowman & Bastedo, 2011), which can lead to extensive exploitation and manipulation by institutions. By the inclusion of star ratings, QS Rankings has commercialized the ranking system and laid excess emphasis on peer review (Anowar et al., 2015). Also, all of these international rankings are limited with a problem of inclusion, especially for institutions in developing countries. This can be a strong reason for several countries to go for national ranking frameworks. The recent introduction of the National Institutional Ranking Framework (NIRF) in India can be an example in this regard. However, all these ranking systems are limited from utilizing the potential of the scholarly output as well as diligent schemes for assessment of institutional research performance. They miss out on various performance factors like (i) the overall multiple thematic expertise and diversity (i.e., at the level of coarse thematic areas) and also, (ii) the multiple thematic expertise at the level of fine thematic areas with a discipline. The first limitation if addressed properly can be useful to inform institutional level policymakers for overall research portfolio management and national level policymakers to plan portfolio management of the scholarly ecosystem of the nation, and also to plan institutionalization to boost overall scholarly output, and for funding agencies to assess research for overall scholarly expertise and diversity. Systematic pursuit of the second limitation can be useful to inform institutional level policymakers for research portfolio management at the level of disciplines, and national level policymakers and funding agencies to assess research for 'thrust-area/national priority area' funding and institutionalization.

Recently, a network and natural language processing (NLP) based framework was introduced by Lathabai et al. (2021 a, b) to address the second limitation, i.e., expertise over a level of fine thematic areas. The authors devised a set of novel indicators, namely, the expertise indicators such as the x -index and the $x(g)$ -index, inspired by principles of the h -index (Hirsch, 2005) and the g -index (Egghe, 2006), that can be determined by the framework. The x -index is supposed to reflect the core competency areas of an institution and the $x(g)$ -index together with the x -index can determine the potential core competency areas (at fine thematic area level within a discipline). This framework was later developed into a recommendation system framework by Lathabai et al. (2022) for institutional collaboration within a discipline so that it will be easier for various stakeholders interested in an institution's performance enhancement or institutions' performance within an ecosystem (such as national level) to work towards excellence in thrust-areas. In this work, we attempt to fill in the gap related to the first limitation at the coarse level of thematic area/subject category, and thus address the issue with the overall scholarly expertise area and diversity.

Though the framework by Lathabai et al. (2021 a, b) is designed for addressing the breadth of the research portfolio, the concept of thematic strengths and expertise determination is so alluring and seems to have an appeal for the overall expertise and diversity determination. This motivated us to explore the possibilities to adapt it for the development of a framework to address the first limitation. So, the framework we introduced is a kind of upward integration of

the framework by Lathabai et al. (2021 a, b), because that framework considered fine thematic areas within a discipline while this framework considers coarse thematic areas in the overall scholarly literature. Now, a suitable classification mechanism that categorizes the overall scholarly literature indexed in scholarly databases such as Web of Science (WoS), Scopus or Dimensions into coarse level thematic areas is required. As such a classification is available in WoS, we use the WoS database for data collection and WoS categories for mapping scholarly literature into thematic classifications (coarse level). These subject categories from WoS were taken since they were annotated by multiple reviewers and are from a reliable source. This mapping facilitates the creation of work (paper)-category affiliation network, thematic strength computation (where suitable attributes such as citations, altmetric score, etc., can be used for strength computation) using network approach (the details of the same is elaborated in ‘Methodology’ section). Now, the ‘Expertise diversity index’ or ‘ x_d -index’, which reflects the top x_d categories that has a strength of at least x_d . These are the core competency (coarse level) areas of an institution. This index is supposed to express the thematic diversity of the research portfolio of an institution too. The validation of the same is done (see results section) and its importance is discussed in the section ‘Discussion’. Now, we can discuss the details of the data and methodology used in our proposed framework.

Data and methodology

Data

As already mentioned, the data collection was carried out from the Web of Science database as it is widely regarded as a reliable source of article meta-data and also WoS subject categories play a crucial role in the framework. For the study, a list of 135 Indian institutions was taken from an ordered list based on the total number of articles published. This list excluded all possible observations of Institutional systems like the IIT System, the CSIR System, etc., and only included the individual institutions and laboratories from these systems. The list of the selected institutions is included in Appendix A. Using this list of institutions, article meta-data was fetched from the WoS database institution-wise. The study intended to showcase the study for the time period of 2011 to 2020, although this framework is capable of being effective for a larger time span if needed.

Since the current work is mainly focused on research performance (measured in terms of publication and citations), only research publication data is used for analysis. This allows to keep focus on the research output of the institutions, thus keeping aside other factors (such as reputation surveys) which are included in various other indexing and ranking frameworks like the Times Higher Education ranking, the ARWU rankings, the QS rankings, and so on. This way, we also eliminate such factors which are not in general very precise ways of measurement or can be manipulated, and solely focus on the research productivity of the institution.

Methodology

The schematic diagram of the proposed framework is shown in fig. 1. Within the data collected for each institution, the following fields of the data were focused on – (i) UT (Unique WOS ID), (ii) Times Cited, All Databases, and (iii) WoS Categories. From these fields, the ‘WoS Categories’ field was used to tag each publication with one or more subject categories, as specified in the Web of Science database. This list of subject categories was chosen because it is a curated list of 254 subject categories and is assigned to each of the publications based on certain factors, including author-provided keywords, indexed keywords, title, and abstract of the article. A total of 409,167 articles were downloaded from the database, with any missing data removed from the dataset. From this data, the fields mentioned before were extracted and

an unweighted affiliation network was built for each of the 135 institutions, mapping each article to one or more subject categories that it represented. This network is denoted as the Work-Category (W-C) network. This affiliation network was then converted to a weighted network, based on the citation data of articles published by an institution from the Times Cited field, which is denoted as the Work-Category* or W-C* network. The choice of citation data is due to the fact that it is the widely recognized proxy of the article’s impact. The conversion of the W-C network into a W-C* network was achieved in a step equivalent to the ‘injection process’, introduced as a part of the ‘injection methodology by Lathabai et al. (2017).

Figure 1. Schematic diagram of the proposed framework

The computation of the x_d -index is the major task for this study, which was achieved by the weighted indegree analysis of W-C* networks. For each node representing a subject category,

the weighted in-degree of the node corresponds to the number of citations received by the institution in the subject category or the strength of an institution in the subject category or the thematic strength of an institution. Now, we are in a position to compute the x_d -index of an institution. Before that, its formal definition is given here.

The framework proposed for the ‘expertise diversity’ determination of institutions based on the ‘ x_d -index’, was inspired by previous work on the x -index, and hence adopted the notion of the h -index. The x_d -index can be defined as:

x_d -index: An institution is supposed to have an x_d -index value of x_d if it has published articles in at least x_d subject categories and has the strength of at least x_d in those x_d categories. These x_d categories would be considered as the x_d -core competent areas of the institution. A high x_d -index value indicates that the institution’s research portfolio is more diverse.

For the computation of x_d -index, standard procedure for determination of h -index can be done. Firstly, subject categories are to be sorted and ranked according to the thematic strength values. The x_d -index of the institution is then computed in an h -index fashion, by computing the Citation-Rank-Ratio (CRR) and identifying the point where the CRR gets below 1. In other terms, the x_d is the first occurrence of one of the following cases –

$$x_d = \begin{cases} r, & \text{if } CRR = \frac{\text{citation at position } r}{r} = 1 \\ r - 1, & \text{if } CRR = \frac{\text{citation at position } r}{r} < 1 \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

So, a WoS category would be considered a core-competency category if $CRR \geq 1$ for that category in the institution.

x_d -index computation is demonstrated by taking Banaras Hindu University (BHU) as an example. BHU has published a total of 11,765 publications (after cleaning the data) within the time period of 2011 and 2020. Out of these publications, 1084 publications were tagged as ‘Materials Science, Multidisciplinary’, 778 publications were tagged as ‘Chemistry, Multidisciplinary’, 765 as ‘Chemistry, Physical’, and so on. There are 206 WoS categories out of all the 254 categories mentioned in the database in which BHU has articles published. Using this data, a mapping between the publications and the tagged categories was done. As publications formed one set (mode) of nodes and categories formed the other set (mode) and the mappings represent edges from the first mode to the second mode, an unweighted affiliation (2 mode) network, namely, the W-C network is formed. Then, the citation data for each publication was ‘injected’ into the network and the unweighted affiliation network is converted into citation weighted affiliation network or the W-C* network. Upon, weighted indegree analysis of the weighted affiliation network, the thematic strengths of BHU in each of the 206 categories can be computed. Upon sorting and computation of CRRs and verifying the criteria (as mentioned in eqn. (1)), the x_d -index can be computed. For BHU, it is found to be 140. That means, BHU has published articles in 140 subject categories that have received at least 140 citations. This value hence corresponds to the core competency areas (coarse level) in the research portfolio of BHU. The x_d indices were computed for all the 135 institutions in a similar manner. The highest value of x_d -index was found to be 140 (Banaras Hindu University) and the lowest value was 36 (Inter University Acceleration Center). The full list of x_d -index values for the top 10 institutions is given in Table 1, and the whole list of 135 institutions is given in Appendix A.

Table 1. List of top institutions according to x_d -index values

<i>Serial no.</i>	<i>Institution</i>	<i>Total publications</i>	<i>x_d-index</i>
1	BANARAS HINDU UNIVERSITY BHU	11765	140
2	INDIAN INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY IIT KHARAGPUR	15498	137
3	INDIAN INSTITUTE OF SCIENCE IISC BANGALORE	18098	132
4	INDIAN INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY IIT DELHI	12938	130
5	INDIAN INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY IIT MADRAS	14132	126
6	INDIAN INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY IIT ROORKEE	10548	125
7	MANIPAL ACADEMY OF HIGHER EDUCATION MAHE	5955	125
8	UNIVERSITY OF CALCUTTA	7405	123
9	INDIAN INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY IIT BOMBAY	13821	122
10	ALIGARH MUSLIM UNIVERSITY	6724	119

It can be seen that though the total publications of BHU is less than the other 4 institutions that are in the top 5 positions, its x_d -index is found to be higher than these. This can strongly indicate the diversity and richness of BHU's research portfolio, which can be attributed to the institution's emphasis to promote research in more diverse fields. This might also indicate the emphasis on interdisciplinary and multi-disciplinary research, which needs to be further investigated because x_d -index is not capable of reflecting that.

Now, the concept of x_d -index can be extended at the national level to reflect the expertise and diversity at the national scholarly ecosystem. For a nation, an institution can be taken as a scholarly entity that reflects a unit of knowledge production just like a thematic area (represented by subject category) is taken as a unit of knowledge production at the institutional level. Then, the 'expertise diversity' index of an institution can represent its strength in the scholarly ecosystem of the nation just like the number of citations can represent thematic strength at the institutional level. This is a kind of nested expertise formation that offers room for the development of nested expertise indices. Here, we develop two nested expertise indices namely the nested x_d -index or xx_d -index and nested $x(g)_d$ -index or $xx(g)_d$ -index with the principles of h and g indices. These are defined as:

xx_d -index: A nation is supposed to have an xx_d -index value of xx_d if it has at least xx_d institutions that has got at least xx_d expertise diversity areas. These xx_d institutions can be considered as the core competent-diverse institutions of the country or institutions with high expertise diversity. A high xx_d -index value indicates that the nation's scholarly research portfolio is diverse and rich.

$xx(g)_d$ -index: A nation is supposed to have an $xx(g)_d$ -index value of $xx(g)_d$ if it has at least $xx(g)_d$ institutions whose institutional expertise diversity indices taken together averages at least $xx(g)_d$. Then, the $xx(g)_d$ - xx_d institutions that follows the top xx_d high expertise diversity

institutions can be considered as potential core competent-diverse institutions of the country or institutions with potential expertise diversity.

Using these two indices, the list of institutions with their x_d -index computed can be grouped into 3 classes –

- **Class 1 or High:** Institutions with x_d -index $\geq xx_d$
- **Class 2 or Moderate:** Institutions whose x_d -index satisfies $xx_d > x_d$ -index $\geq xx(g)_d$
- **Class 3 or Low:** Institutions whose x_d -index satisfies $xx(g)_d > x_d$ -index

These three classes were regarded as group of institutions with high diversity (Class 1), group of institutions with medium diversity (Class 2), and group of institutions with low diversity (Class 3). This grouping was performed to prioritize the recommendation section of the study since the low diversity institutions have a greater need to improve their score and contribute to the overall diversity of the country. The two indices, i.e., xx_d -index and $xx(g)_d$ -index were computed to be 74 and 91. Hence, all the institutions in the dataset having an $xx(g)_d$ -index greater than 91 was taken into the last class (Class 3). More analysis based on the sections is provided in the Discussions section later in the article.

Results

The x_d -index for all the 135 institutions is computed and shown in Appendix A. The x_d -index framework developed in this study is unique, since it can efficiently determine how many different fields/categories an institution is working on from scholarly publication list of that institution. Therefore, an accurate and comparative validation of the system’s performance with existing ranking systems and frameworks that are not purely based on publication data is not possible. Another hinderance is the underrepresentation of Indian institutions in these rankings. Despite this, we are attempting such a comparative validation by using commonly listed institutions in a pair of ‘ x_d based list vs existing ranking-based list’, where latest edition of the popular international overall ranking schemes of QS, ARWU, THE and CWTS Leiden rankings are used for determination of existing ranking-based list, hoping that it still can signal the novelty/non-obviousness of the proposed framework. As already mentioned, in most of these rankings, the Indian institutions are underrepresented due to multiple factors, and hence have less data. Hence, a small number out of the 135 institutions are represented only in these rankings as commonly listed institutions. Spearman Correlation Coefficient ρ of x_d with these rankings are given in Table 2.

Table 2. Popular International Institutional rankings and their ranked correlation

<i>Ranking</i>	<i>Number of common institutions</i>	<i>Spearman Correlation Coefficient ρ</i>
ARWU	12	0.39544
THE	48	0.18826
QS	32	0.46724
CWTS Leiden	44	0.78661

From the table, it can be observed that the ARWU Shanghai ranking, the Times Higher Education ranking as well as the QS World University rankings have a low correlation score with the proposed x_d -index based rankings. This may be because these rankings bring in many factors within their internal ranking score. Only CWTS Leiden ranking can be seen to have a somewhat positive correlation, since it emphasizes the publication-based factors more into their ranking score as compared to others. These results shows that the x_d -index framework can generate essentially different rankings from most other prevalent ranking systems.

Since the x_d -index framework was designed with the h -index principle, a correlation between the two indices was also computed. The h -index of the institution was computed in the way mentioned by Hirsch (2005) where a score of h was given to an institution which had h publications with at least h citations. Indian Institute of Science, Bangalore had the highest h -index of 160, while Inter University Acceleration Centre had the lowest score of 46. A Spearman Rank Correlation was computed between the x_d -index and h -index, and the ρ value is 0.5786. Similarly, upon computation of the correlation of x_d -index and g -index, the ρ value is 0.4207. These not-so strong correlation values may indicate that institutional h -index if used for ranking institutional performance might produce significantly different results and such an assessment might neither reflect the expertise nor the diversity of the institutions. This conviction is also validated next.

Since the proposed framework focuses more on the scholarly expertise diversity of the institution, correlation analysis of the x_d -index with standard diversity measure value is also computed. This was done by computing the Shannon's Entropy value of an institution based on the distribution of citations earned by the institution with respect to the subject categories, for every institution. It measures the evenness and richness of the strength of the institution in subject categories. The ranked correlation between the Shannon's diversity index (based on Shannon's entropy) and the x_d -index is 0.86879. On the other hand, the ranked correlation between the Shannon's diversity index and h -index is 0.26028, and that between Shannon's diversity index and g -index is 0.17569. This demonstrates that for research portfolio management that requires capturing of expertise and diversity of an institution, an index that represents the overall expertise diversity is better than indicators such as the h and g indices that are supposed to represent the quantity and quality of publications.

Discussion

As already discussed, the overall expertise index computed using WoS categories reflects the core competency areas (at a coarse level) of an institution. Higher the value of x_d -index, higher would be the diversity of the institution. h -index (in this case the institutional h -index), which served as the inspiration for the development of x_d -index, neither reflects the core competency at a coarse level (at any level for that matter) nor is capable of indicating the diversity of the research portfolio of an institution. Moreover, the correlation between h and x_d is found to be moderate unlike the strong correlation of the x -index (that reflects the core competency of an institution in a discipline) and the h -index of the institution in a discipline. This eliminates any speculation of information redundancy and strengthens the conviction of novelty of the x_d -index. Though, the x -index does not provide overall expertise and diversity of the research portfolio of the institution and it is not prudent to compare the computation of the x -index with computation of the x_d -index, it is still worth mentioning that the framework for the x_d -index is much simpler as it does not require NLP module.

So, when it comes to the performance assessment of an institution with an objective to determine the overall scholarly performance of an institution and core competency areas, the

framework devised in this work that uses coarse level thematic classification as represented by WoS categories and computation of x_d -index is suitable. But when fine level thematic strength within a discipline is required, a framework that uses the x -index would be recommended. In other words, when an institutional research portfolio is required to be studied, the proposed framework is useful and when a discipline level research portfolio of an institution is required to be understood, the x -index based framework is to be used. x -index based assessment will help to make decisions on whether an existing department have to start a new academic course/research lab or to train an existing faculty/researcher in thematic areas that are not within its core competency within a discipline or to pick suitable faculty member/researcher/group to collaborate with their peers working on the concerned thematic areas in other institutions. The proposed framework can be used even to gain insights that will help to determine whether an institution needs to altogether start a new department (hire faculty members, start academic/research programs and various allied activities, etc.) to work towards the expansion of its scholarly diversity.

Moreover, the application of x_d -index can be expanded to reflect the national level expertise and diversity in the form of nested (coarse level) expertise indices such as nested x_d -index or xx_d -index and nested $x(g)_d$ -index or $xx(g)_d$ -index. As already mentioned, India's xx_d -index is found to be 74, which indicates that India has at least 74 institutions that have at least 74 coarse level core competency areas. This can be considered as core competent-diverse institutions of the country or institutions with high expertise diversity. Also, there are 17 institutions ($xx(g)_d - xx_d = 91-74=17$) that can be considered as potential core competent-diverse institutions of the country or institutions with potential expertise diversity. Thus, the nested expertise indices (at coarse level) or nested expertise diversity indices partition the dataset of 135 institutions into three categories- high (core competent-diverse), moderate (potential core competent-diverse) and low (the rest). These categories consist of 74, 17 and 44 institutions respectively. This is a kind of classification of the scholarly (organizational) portfolio of the country. This classification may help national level policymakers to devise strategies for strengthening the diversity of the national scholarly ecosystem. This classification along with the classification of their research portfolio into core competency areas might help institutional level policymakers to devise research portfolio diversity enhancement strategies. Some directions for a course of action to be taken by national level and institutional decision-makers based on the analysis of the set of 135 institutions in India are given below:

National level policymakers

National level policymakers are informed of the 74 most core competent and diverse institutions and 17 potential competent and diverse institutions in the national scholarly ecosystem that embeds the science and technology ecosystem. This information can be used to:

- Develop policies for the establishment of novel regional research collaboration among academic and research institutions (A2A), between academic and research institutions and research institutions by Government (A2G), between academic and research institutions and industry (A2I) and even for establishment of regional innovation clusters
- Develop policies to facilitate international collaboration (academic and industrial) to enhance the expertise of 74 core competent and diverse institutions as well as to enhance the expertise and expand the diversity of 17 potential core competent and diverse institutions

Institutional level policymakers

Institutional level policymakers are informed of the overall classification using nested expertise and diversity indices and the category/class in which they belong to. This information can be used by institutions in different categories to form their own policies for research portfolio management (either expansion of diversity or enhancement of expertise or both) other than striving constantly for improving their strengths in the thematic areas that are already part of the core competency list of an institution by measures such as looking for international and industrial collaboration in these areas or other areas.

- Institutions in the high diversity category
 - May primarily look for the improvement of diversity by enhancing some relatively strong areas other than core competency coarse level thematic areas by pairing with suitable institutions in the same category having these areas as core competency areas,
 - May secondarily look for the improvement of diversity by enhancing some relatively strong areas other than core competency coarse level thematic areas by pairing with suitable institutions in the medium category having these areas as core competency areas,
 - May thirdly look for the adoption of expansion of diversity by focusing on some weak areas too or even opening accounts in some weak areas eyeing for benefit in the not-so-immediate future by pairing with suitable institutions in the same category having these areas as core competency areas.

- Institutions in the medium diversity category
 - May primarily look for the improvement of diversity by enhancing some relatively strong areas other than core competency coarse level thematic areas by pairing with suitable institutions in the high diversity category having these areas as core competency areas,
 - May secondarily look for the improvement of diversity by enhancing some relatively strong areas other than core competency coarse level thematic areas by pairing with suitable institutions in the same category having these areas as core competency areas,
 - May thirdly look for the adoption of expansion of diversity by focusing on a large number of weak areas too and even opening accounts in some weak areas (than required by high diversity category) eyeing for benefit in not-so-immediate future by pairing with suitable institutions in the high diversity category and same category having these areas as core competency areas,
 - May lastly look for the adoption of expansion of diversity by focusing on some weak areas too and even opening accounts in some weak areas eyeing for benefit in not-so-immediate future by pairing with suitable institutions in the low diversity category having these areas as core competency areas or some relatively strong areas other than core competency areas.

- Institutions in the low diversity category
 - May primarily look for the improvement of diversity by enhancing some relatively strong areas other than core competency coarse level thematic areas by pairing with suitable institutions in the higher diversity categories having these areas as core competency areas,

- May secondarily look for the improvement of diversity by enhancing some relatively strong areas other than core competency coarse level thematic areas by pairing with suitable institutions in the same category having these areas as core competency areas,
- May thirdly look for the adoption of expansion of diversity by focusing on a large number of weak areas too and even opening accounts in so many weak areas (than required by higher diversity categories) eyeing for benefit in not-so-immediate future by pairing with suitable institutions in the higher diversity categories and same category having these areas as core competency areas,
- May lastly look for the adoption of expansion of diversity by focusing on some weak areas too and even opening accounts in some weak areas eyeing for benefit in not-so-immediate future by pairing with suitable institutions in the same category having these areas as relatively strong areas other than core competency areas.

This indicator can, thus help in providing a ranking based on the subject diversity of an institution. Although for most of the institution this would be beneficial to increase the overall diversity and strength of their research portfolio, this would also help subject focused institutions like medical colleges and business schools to analyze which category they are lacking on, within their own subject field. Taking an example of “INDIAN INSTITUTE OF SCIENCE IISC BANGALORE”, the index and the corresponding core-competent categories can be used to confirm any subject category related to STEM which the institution may be lacking in. Even though our framework has the capability to assess the overall diversity of the research portfolio of an institution, the institution themselves can utilise the methods to select the subject areas most similar to their current research portfolio.

With our proposed indicator, although we can calculate the diversity of institutions, it has been demonstrated for a specific dataset obtained from the Web of Science database. The robustness of the framework proposed can be reaffirmed if it is executed for data from other databases, such as the Scopus or Dimensions database. This would also be done if a larger dataset for other countries were to be taken as well. This is proposed to be taken up as future work.

Conclusion

In this work, we have devised an indicator namely, the x_d -index, that can reflect the overall scholarly expertise of an institution, and also the diversity of an institution in terms of the number of coarse level core competent thematic areas it possesses as part of its research portfolio. Unlike the h -index, from which motivation is drawn for its design, its ability to reflect diversity is successfully validated with a positive outcome. Also, unlike the recently introduced x -index based framework by Lathabai et al. (2021), the proposed framework based on x_d -index (which can be treated as a kind of upward-integration to serve the purpose of overall scholarly expertise determination of institutions) is much simpler as it does not require NLP module. Further, using the notion of nested (coarse level) expertise indices such as xx_d and $xx(g)_d$ indices, a nation’s scholarly portfolio can be classified into classes such as high expertise diversity class (or high), potential expertise diversity class (or moderate) and the rest (or low).

This classification may aid national level policymakers to manage the scholarly portfolio in effective way to strengthen the scholarly ecosystem that includes the Science and Technology ecosystem of the nation. At the institutional level also, this classification along with the distinction imparted on the research portfolio of the institution via x_d -index may help to explore possibilities to forge effective policies for research portfolio management of the institution. Some directive actions for both institutional and national policymakers are provided in this regard.

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Appendix A

<i>Sr. No.</i>	<i>Institution</i>	<i>Total Publications</i>	<i>x_a-index</i>
1	ACADEMY OF SCIENTIFIC INNOVATIVE RESEARCH ACSIR	9972	98
2	ALAGAPPA UNIVERSITY	2347	81
3	ALIGARH MUSLIM UNIVERSITY	6724	119
4	ALL INDIA INSTITUTE OF MEDICAL SCIENCES AIIMS NEW DELHI	8959	103
5	AMITY UNIVERSITY NOIDA	2405	100
6	AMRITA VISHWA VIDYAPEETHAM	2856	101
7	ANDHRA UNIVERSITY	2093	81
8	ANNA UNIVERSITY	9960	110
9	ANNAMALAI UNIVERSITY	3976	95
10	BANARAS HINDU UNIVERSITY BHU	11765	140
11	BHARATHIAR UNIVERSITY	4262	97
12	BHARATHIDASAN UNIVERSITY	3139	89
13	BIRLA INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY MESRA	2276	87
14	BIRLA INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY SCIENCE PILANI BITS PILANI	4616	109
15	BOSE INSTITUTE	2016	67
16	CHRISTIAN MEDICAL COLLEGE HOSPITAL CMCH VELLORE	2718	68
17	COCHIN UNIVERSITY SCIENCE TECHNOLOGY	2386	89
18	CSIR CENTRAL DRUG RESEARCH INSTITUTE CDRI	3068	69
19	CSIR CENTRAL ELECTROCHEMICAL RESEARCH INSTITUTE CECRI	2244	51
20	CSIR CENTRAL FOOD TECHNOLOGICAL RESEARCH INSTITUTE CFTRI	1939	52
21	CSIR CENTRAL GLASS CERAMIC RESEARCH INSTITUTE CGCRI	1664	50
22	CSIR CENTRAL LEATHER RESEARCH INSTITUTE CLRI	2023	64
23	CSIR CENTRAL SALT MARINE CHEMICAL RESEARCH INSTITUTE CSMCRI	1991	55
24	CSIR CENTRE FOR CELLULAR MOLECULAR BIOLOGY CCMB	1000	57
25	CSIR INDIAN INSTITUTE OF CHEMICAL BIOLOGY IICB	1961	70
26	CSIR INDIAN INSTITUTE OF CHEMICAL TECHNOLOGY IICT	6153	72
27	CSIR INSTITUTE OF GENOMICS INTEGRATIVE BIOLOGY IGIB	1408	69
28	CSIR NATIONAL CHEMICAL LABORATORY NCL	4930	69
29	CSIR NATIONAL INSTITUTE INTERDISCIPLINARY SCIENCE TECHNOLOGY NIIST	2059	59
30	CSIR NATIONAL INSTITUTE OF OCEANOGRAPHY NIO	1995	54
31	CSIR NATIONAL PHYSICAL LABORATORY NPL	3476	63
32	DELHI TECHNOLOGICAL UNIVERSITY	1973	92
33	DR B R AMBEDKAR NATIONAL INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY JALANDHAR	1640	72
34	GAUHATI UNIVERSITY	1814	76
35	GOVT MED COLL	1187	58
36	GURU NANAK DEV UNIVERSITY	3371	91
37	ICAR INDIAN AGRICULTURAL RESEARCH INSTITUTE	5123	65
38	ICAR INDIAN VETERINARY RESEARCH INSTITUTE	2716	54

<i>Sr. No.</i>	<i>Institution</i>	<i>Total Publications</i>	<i>x_a-index</i>
39	ICAR NATIONAL DAIRY RESEARCH INSTITUTE	2260	45
40	INDIAN ASSOCIATION FOR THE CULTIVATION OF SCIENCE IACS JADAVPUR	4526	53
41	INDIAN INSTITUTE OF ENGINEERING SCIENCE TECHNOLOGY SHIBPUR IEST	3342	82
42	INDIAN INSTITUTE OF SCIENCE EDUCATION RESEARCH IISER BHOPAL	1830	59
43	INDIAN INSTITUTE OF SCIENCE EDUCATION RESEARCH IISER KOLKATA	2915	80
44	INDIAN INSTITUTE OF SCIENCE EDUCATION RESEARCH IISER MOHALI	1771	60
45	INDIAN INSTITUTE OF SCIENCE IISC BANGALORE	18098	132
46	INDIAN INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY IIT BHU VARANASI	5121	99
47	INDIAN INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY IIT BOMBAY	13821	122
48	INDIAN INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY IIT DELHI	12938	130
49	INDIAN INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY IIT GANDHINAGAR	1673	73
50	INDIAN INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY IIT GUWAHATI	8582	114
51	INDIAN INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY IIT HYDERABAD	3186	89
52	INDIAN INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY IIT INDORE	3169	84
53	INDIAN INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY IIT KANPUR	9882	116
54	INDIAN INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY IIT KHARAGPUR	15498	137
55	INDIAN INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY IIT MADRAS	14132	126
56	INDIAN INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY IIT PATNA	1818	72
57	INDIAN INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY IIT ROORKEE	10548	125
58	INDIAN INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY IIT ROPAR	1718	76
59	INDIAN INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY INDIAN SCHOOL OF MINES DHANBAD	6040	99
60	INDIAN SPACE RESEARCH ORGANISATION ISRO	4041	72
61	INDIAN STATISTICAL INSTITUTE	3845	95
62	INDIRA GANDHI CENTRE FOR ATOMIC RESEARCH IGCAR	3831	70
63	INSTITUTE OF CHEMICAL TECHNOLOGY MUMBAI	3780	66
64	INTER UNIVERSITY ACCELERATOR CENTRE	1691	36
65	JADAVPUR UNIVERSITY	9427	115
66	JAMIA HAMDARD UNIVERSITY	2904	82
67	JAMIA MILLIA ISLAMIA	4155	110
68	JAWAHARLAL INSTITUTE OF POSTGRADUATE MEDICAL EDUCATION RESEARCH	1409	51
69	JAWAHARLAL NEHRU CENTER FOR ADVANCED SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH JNCASR	2992	66
70	JAWAHARLAL NEHRU TECHNOLOGICAL UNIVERSITY HYDERABAD	1758	72
71	JAWAHARLAL NEHRU UNIVERSITY NEW DELHI	4927	111
72	KALINGA INSTITUTE OF INDUSTRIAL TECHNOLOGY KIIT	1000	88
73	KALYANI UNIVERSITY	2135	80
74	KASTURBA MEDICAL COLLEGE MANIPAL	1411	71
75	KURUKSHETRA UNIVERSITY	1665	78
76	L V PRASAD EYE INSTITUTE	1541	39
77	LOVELY PROFESSIONAL UNIVERSITY	1658	78

<i>Sr. No.</i>	<i>Institution</i>	<i>Total Publications</i>	<i>x_a-index</i>
78	LUCKNOW UNIVERSITY	1979	80
79	MADURAI KAMARAJ UNIVERSITY	2273	73
80	MAHARAJA SAYAJIRAO UNIVERSITY BARODA	2219	88
81	MAHARSHI DAYANAND UNIVERSITY	1585	73
82	MAHATMA GANDHI UNIVERSITY KERALA	1568	69
83	MALAVIYA NATIONAL INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY JAIPUR	2169	80
84	MANIPAL ACADEMY OF HIGHER EDUCATION MAHE	5955	125
85	MAULANA AZAD MEDICAL COLLEGE	1198	45
86	MOTILAL NEHRU NATIONAL INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY	1966	74
87	NATIONAL CENTRE FOR BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES NCBS	1512	64
88	NATIONAL INSTITUTE OF MENTAL HEALTH NEUROSCIENCES INDIA	2498	61
89	NATIONAL INSTITUTE OF PHARMACEUTICAL EDUCATION RESEARCH S A S NAGAR MOHALI	1444	57
90	NATIONAL INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY CALICUT	1838	80
91	NATIONAL INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY DURGAPUR	2401	82
92	NATIONAL INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY KARNATAKA	2833	84
93	NATIONAL INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY KURUKSHETRA	1674	71
94	NATIONAL INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY ROURKELA	4938	107
95	NATIONAL INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY SILCHAR	1657	66
96	NATIONAL INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY TIRUCHIRAPPALLI	4229	82
97	NATIONAL INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY WARANGAL	2204	71
98	PHYSICAL RESEARCH LABORATORY INDIA	2137	43
99	PONDICHERRY UNIVERSITY	3171	96
100	POST GRADUATE INSTITUTE OF MEDICAL EDUCATION RESEARCH PGIMER CHANDIGARH	6441	85
101	PUNJAB AGRICULTURAL UNIVERSITY	2464	56
102	PUNJABI UNIVERSITY	2273	96
103	RAJA RAMANNA CENTRE FOR ADVANCED TECHNOLOGY	1803	47
104	RASHTRASANT TUKADOJI MAHARAJ NAGPUR UNIVERSITY	1535	66
105	SANJAY GANDHI POSTGRADUATE INSTITUTE OF MEDICAL SCIENCES	2256	66
106	SARDAR VALLABHBHAI NATIONAL INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY	2140	80
107	SATHYABAMA INSTITUTE OF SCIENCE TECHNOLOGY	1543	74
108	SAVITRIBAI PHULE PUNE UNIVERSITY	4246	98
109	SETH GORDHANDAS SUNDERDAS MEDICAL COLLEGE KING EDWARD MEMORIAL HOSPITAL	1059	52
110	SHANMUGHA ARTS SCIENCE TECHNOLOGY RESEARCH ACADEMY SASTRA	3354	95
111	SHIVAJI UNIVERSITY	2467	70
112	SIKSHA O ANUSANDHAN UNIVERSITY	1946	80
113	SN BOSE NATIONAL CENTRE FOR BASIC SCIENCE SBNBCBS	1954	49
114	SREE CHITRA TIRUNAL INSTITUTE FOR MEDICAL SCIENCES TECHNOLOGY SCTIMST	1323	64
115	SRI VENKATESWARA UNIVERSITY	2361	75
116	SRM INSTITUTE OF SCIENCE TECHNOLOGY CHENNAI	4640	106
117	SSN COLLEGE OF ENGINEERING	1613	59

<i>Sr. No.</i>	<i>Institution</i>	<i>Total Publications</i>	<i>x_a-index</i>
118	ST JOHN S NATIONAL ACADEMY OF HEALTH SCIENCES	1209	60
119	TATA MEMORIAL CENTRE TMC	2353	63
120	TATA MEMORIAL HOSPITAL	2006	59
121	TEZPUR UNIVERSITY	2742	90
122	THAPAR INSTITUTE OF ENGINEERING TECHNOLOGY	5141	98
123	UGC DAE CONSORTIUM FOR SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH	2245	43
124	UNIVERSITY COLLEGE OF MEDICAL SCIENCES	1033	54
125	UNIVERSITY OF ALLAHABAD	2335	94
126	UNIVERSITY OF BURDWAN	2161	84
127	UNIVERSITY OF CALCUTTA	7405	123
128	UNIVERSITY OF HYDERABAD	5361	102
129	UNIVERSITY OF JAMMU	1644	66
130	UNIVERSITY OF KASHMIR	1879	89
131	UNIVERSITY OF MADRAS	3324	89
132	UNIVERSITY OF MYSORE	2253	76
133	UNIVERSITY OF RAJASTHAN	1712	75
134	VELLORE INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY	8153	118
135	VISVESVARAYA NATIONAL INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY NAGPUR	2129	80